

Determinants of Hematological Indices among Pregnant Women: The Role of Trimester, Abortion History, and Socio-Demographic Factors

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Abstract

Background: Pregnancy induces profound hematological changes that may obscure the distinction between physiologic adaptation and pathological anemia. Monitoring hemoglobin (Hb), packed cell volume (PCV), and serum iron is essential for ensuring maternal health and favorable perinatal outcomes. This study aimed to explore trimester-related changes in hematological indices and their association with socio-demographic and reproductive factors among pregnant women. **Methods:** A cross-sectional study was conducted on 150 pregnant women attending antenatal care at Al-Najaf health directorate between [march–April, 2025] Participants aged 18–40 years with singleton pregnancies were included, while women with systemic illness or hematologic disorders were excluded. Data on demographic characteristics, reproductive history, and antenatal attendance were collected via structured interviews. Venous blood samples were analyzed for Hb and PCV using an automated hematology analyzer, and serum iron was measured by a standardized colorimetric method. **Results:** Most participants were young (<30 years, 76.7%), rural residents (62%), and overweight (50%), with the majority being housewives (90%). Hemoglobin and PCV values showed a significant decline in the third trimester (Hb: 9.99 ± 0.83 g/dL, PCV: $30.20 \pm 2.29\%$) compared to earlier trimesters ($p=0.02$ and $p=0.05$, respectively). Serum iron was unexpectedly higher among women with abortion history (45.71 ± 27.86 $\mu\text{g/dL}$, $p=0.02$) and lower among employed women (28.65 ± 17.25 $\mu\text{g/dL}$, $p=0.05$). Other demographic factors showed no significant impact. **Conclusion:** Trimester progression was the primary determinant of Hb and PCV, reflecting physiological hemodilution. Serum iron variation with abortion history and occupation highlights the role of reproductive experiences and lifestyle in maternal iron status. These findings underscore the importance of trimester-specific monitoring and targeted antenatal interventions to optimize maternal hematologic health.

Introduction

Pregnancy imposes significant adjustments on the maternal hematologic system, necessitating careful evaluation of red blood cell indices and iron status to distinguish physiological changes from pathologic anemia. During gestation, plasma volume increases by approximately 40–60%, whereas red cell mass expands by only 20–50%, resulting in a relative hemodilution and a physiologic decline in hemoglobin (Hb) and hematocrit (or packed cell volume, PCV) values [1,2].

Although mild “dilutional anemia” is expected, identification of true iron deficiency or other pathological states remains critical, since untreated anemia during pregnancy is associated with increased risks of preterm birth, low birth weight, maternal fatigue, and adverse perinatal outcomes [3-5]. Globally, iron deficiency is the most common cause of non-physiologic anemia in pregnancy, accounting for up to 75% of cases [6]. The World Health Organization estimates that approximately 40–45% of pregnant

More Information

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women in developing regions are anemic, often due to inadequate dietary iron intake, poor absorption, increased demands, and losses [7]. The iron requirement increases markedly over trimesters: roughly 0.8 mg/day in the first trimester, escalating to 4–5 mg/day in the second, and exceeding 6 mg/day in the third trimester to support fetal growth, placental development, and expansion of maternal erythropoiesis [8,9]. Key laboratory indicators used in evaluating maternal hematologic health include hemoglobin concentration, PCV, and serum iron levels. Hemoglobin and PCV are routinely measured due to their low cost and ease of assessment, but they may lack sensitivity or specificity for detecting early iron deficiency, especially in the first trimester [10]. Serum iron reflects circulating iron bound to transferrin, but is subject to diurnal variation and is influenced by recent dietary intake or use of iron supplements, limiting its reliability as a standalone marker [11]. The study aims to examine the trimester-based differences in Hb, PCV, and serum iron in pregnant women, and to assess the influence of socio-demographic factors, reproductive history, and occupation on these hematologic indices.

Method

This cross-sectional, descriptive study was designed to evaluate hematological parameters among pregnant women and to assess the influence of demographic, socioeconomic, and reproductive factors. A total of 150 pregnant women attending antenatal care at Al-Najaf health directorate between [march–April, 2025] were recruited using a convenience sampling technique. Eligible participants were aged 18–40 years with singleton pregnancies. Women with known hematological disorders, chronic systemic illnesses (renal, hepatic, or cardiac disease), multiple gestations, or a recent history of blood transfusion were excluded to avoid confounding effects on hematologic indices. Following informed consent, each participant was interviewed using a structured questionnaire that collected socio-demographic data (age, residency, education, occupation, and income), reproductive history (gravidity, parity, abortion, use of oral contraceptive pills, and gestational trimester), and antenatal care attendance. Height and weight were measured to calculate body mass index (BMI), which

was classified according to World Health Organization (WHO) standards. Venous blood samples (5 mL) were drawn under aseptic conditions. Hemoglobin concentration and packed cell volume (PCV) were determined using an automated hematology analyzer, which was calibrated daily to ensure accuracy. Serum iron levels were assessed using a standardized colorimetric method, with internal quality controls applied. All analyses were performed in the same laboratory to minimize variability. Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 24 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Group comparisons of mean hemoglobin, PCV, and serum iron according to socio-demographic and reproductive variables were performed using independent t-tests or one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), as appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee (Approval No. 144, dated 1 April 2025), and all procedures were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Results

The majority of participants were **under 30 years (76.7%)**, while only 23.3% were ≥30 years. Most women were **overweight (50%)**, followed by normal BMI (36%) and obese (14%). Residency distribution showed a rural predominance (**62% rural vs. 38% urban**). Regarding education, the largest group had only **primary education (38%)**, while secondary and higher education each accounted for 26.7%. Illiteracy was relatively low (8.7%). Socioeconomically, most participants reported **fair income (80.7%)** compared to only 19.3% with good income. Occupational status was strikingly imbalanced, with **housewives representing 90%** and only 10% being employed. The sample represents a young, predominantly rural, overweight population with limited education and socioeconomic resources. The very high proportion of housewives may reflect cultural and regional norms, and this could influence nutritional status, antenatal care utilization, and anemia prevalence. As in table 1.

Table 1: Patient’s Demographic Profile

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gravida	<3	71	47.3
	≥3	79	52.7
Parity	no	46	30.7
	1-3	90	60.0
	>3	14	9.3
Abortion	no	127	84.7
	yes	23	15.3
Oral contraceptive pills Used	no	101	67.3

	<i>yes</i>	49	32.7
Trimester of Gestation	<i>1st</i>	13	8.7
	<i>2nd</i>	63	42.0
	<i>3rd</i>	74	49.3
Antenatal care	<i>no</i>	50	33.3
	<i>1-3 times</i>	100	66.7

Parity and reproductive history show that most women were **multigravida (≥ 3 pregnancies: 52.7%)**. Parity distribution highlighted that **60% had 1–3 children**, 30.7% had none, and only 9.3% had more than three children. **Abortions were reported in 15.3%** of participants, while the majority (84.7%) had no abortion history. **OCP use was relatively common (32.7%)**. Regarding pregnancy stage, almost half of the women were in the **third trimester (49.3%)**, followed

by the second (42%) and only 8.7% in the first. **Antenatal care attendance was suboptimal:** 33.3% had no ANC visits, while 66.7% had only 1–3 visits. The data reflect a population with high fertility, limited ANC utilization, and a significant proportion with abortion history. Late-trimester presentation suggests delayed health-seeking behavior, which may affect maternal hematological indices. As in table 2.

Table 2: Patient’s Genecology History

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Gravida	<i><3</i>	71	47.3
	<i>≥ 3</i>	79	52.7
Parity	<i>no</i>	46	30.7
	<i>1-3</i>	90	60.0
	<i>>3</i>	14	9.3
Abortion	<i>no</i>	127	84.7
	<i>yes</i>	23	15.3
Oral contraceptive pills used	<i>no</i>	101	67.3
	<i>yes</i>	49	32.7
Trimester of Gestation	<i>1st</i>	13	8.7
	<i>2nd</i>	63	42.0
	<i>3rd</i>	74	49.3
Antenatal care	<i>no</i>	50	33.3
	<i>1-3 times</i>	100	66.7

Age: Hb did not significantly differ between <30 (10.18 ± 0.75) and ≥ 30 years (10.11 ± 0.84) ($p=0.6$). **BMI:** Overweight women had slightly higher Hb (10.23 ± 0.76) compared to normal (10.16 ± 0.74) and obese (9.95 ± 0.88), though not significant ($p=0.3$). **Education:** Hb was comparable across education levels ($p=0.7$). **Trimester:** A significant drop was noted in the **third trimester (9.99 ± 0.83)** compared to earlier trimesters

($p=0.02$). **Other factors (residency, income, occupation, gravida, abortion, OCP use, parity):** No significant differences were observed. Trimester was the main determinant of Hb, highlighting **physiological hemodilution in late pregnancy**. Other demographic and socioeconomic factors showed little effect on mean Hb. As in table 3.

Table 3: Differences Mean of Hb (g/dL) According to Study Variables

Parameter	Age Group	Mean \pm SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	<30 years	10.18 ± 0.75	0.6
	≥ 30 years	10.11 ± 0.84	
Parameter	BMI	Mean \pm SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	Normal	10.16 ± 0.74	0.3
	Overweight	10.23 ± 0.76	
	Obese	9.95 ± 0.88	
Parameter	Education	Mean \pm SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	Illiterate	10.23 ± 0.97	0.7
	Primary	10.07 ± 0.78	
	Secondary	10.19 ± 0.76	

Parameter	Higher	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	1st	10.32 ± 0.53	0.02
	2nd	10.34 ± 0.69	
	3rd	9.99 ± 0.83	
Parameter	Abortion	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	No	10.15 ± 0.62	0.9
	1-3	10.17 ± 0.84	
Parameter	Residency	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	Rural	10.15 ± 0.80	0.8
	Urban	10.18 ± 0.72	
Parameter	Income	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	Fair	10.17 ± 0.80	0.9
	Good	10.16 ± 0.62	
Parameter	Occupation	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	Housewife	10.16 ± 0.78	0.6
	Employed	10.25 ± 0.68	
Parameter	Gravida	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	<3	10.08 ± 0.85	0.2
	≥3	10.24 ± 0.68	
Parameter	Abortion	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	No	10.18 ± 0.77	0.6
	Yes	10.10 ± 0.75	
Parameter	OCP	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	No	10.12 ± 0.84	0.3
	Yes	10.26 ± 0.61	
Parameter	Parity	Mean ± SD	P-value
Hb (g/dL)	No	9.99 ± 0.88	0.2
	1-3	10.24 ± 0.73	
	>3	10.280.51	

Age, BMI, education, residency, income, occupation, gravida, abortion, OCP use, parity: No significant differences. **Trimester:** PCV was significantly lower in the third trimester (30.20 ± 2.29) compared to first (31.15 ± 1.56) and second (31.04 ± 2.12), p=0.05.

Similar to Hb, PCV reduction was strongly associated with trimester, reflecting normal pregnancy physiology but possibly exacerbated by nutritional or iron deficiencies. As in table 4.

Table 4: Differences Mean of PCV (%) According to Study Variables

Parameter	Age Group	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	<30 years	30.70 ± 2.13	0.5
	≥30 years	30.42 ± 2.43	
Parameter	BMI	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	Normal	30.65 ± 2.03	0.2
	Overweight	30.82 ± 2.29	
	Obese	29.93 ± 2.23	
Parameter	Education	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	Illiterate	30.77 ± 2.71	0.7
	Primary	30.41 ± 2.21	
	Secondary	30.67 ± 2.18	
	Higher	30.88 ± 2.06	
Parameter	Trimester	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	1st	31.15 ± 1.56	0.05
	2nd	31.04 ± 2.12	
	3rd	30.20 ± 2.29	

Parameter	Abortion	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	No	30.47 ± 1.71	0.5
	1-3	30.72 ± 2.41	
Parameter	Residency	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	Rural	30.58 ± 2.27	0.6
	Urban	30.73 ± 2.09	
Parameter	Income	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	Fair	30.64 ± 2.33	0.9
	Good	30.64 ± 1.57	
Parameter	Occupation	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	Housewife	30.61 ± 2.24	0.6
	Employed	30.85 ± 1.76	
Parameter	Gravida	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	<3	30.48 ± 2.42	0.4
	≥3	30.78 ± 1.98	
Parameter	Abortion	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	No	30.66 ± 2.24	0.7
	Yes	30.48 ± 1.97	
Parameter	OCP	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	No	30.59 ± 2.36	0.6
	Yes	30.74 ± 1.82	
Parameter	Parity	Mean ± SD	P-value
PCV (%)	No	30.24 ± 2.62	0.3
	1-3	30.81 ± 2.02	
	>3	30.821.64	

Age, BMI, education, trimester, residency, income, gravida, OCP use, parity: No significant association. **Abortion history:** Women with abortion had significantly higher serum iron (45.71 ± 27.86) than those without (34.66 ± 20.78), p=0.02. **Occupation:** Housewives had higher serum iron (37.21 ± 22.64) compared to employed women (28.65 ± 17.25), p=0.05. **Abortion frequency:** 1-3 abortions associated with

higher serum iron than no abortions (38.54 ± 24.01 vs. 31.99 ± 17.68, p=0.05). Unlike Hb and PCV, serum iron showed unexpected variation with abortion history and occupation. The higher levels among women with abortions may reflect supplementation post-abortion or altered iron metabolism. The lower iron in employed women might be linked to stress, dietary patterns, or irregular supplementation. As in table 5.

Table 5: Differences Mean of Serum Iron (µg/dL) According to Study Variables

Parameter	Age Group	Mean ± SD	P-value
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	<30 years	36.65 ± 21.83	0.7
	≥30 years	35.40 ± 23.94	
Parameter	BMI	Mean ± SD	P-value
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	Normal	30.65 ± 2.03	0.5
	Overweight	30.82 ± 2.29	
	Obese	29.93 ± 2.23	
Parameter	Education	Mean ± SD	P-value
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	Illiterate	32.64 ± 22.50	0.5
	Primary	35.60 ± 20.08	
	Secondary	34.27 ± 23.05	
	Higher	40.73 ± 24.46	
Parameter	Trimester	Mean ± SD	P-value
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	1st	34.72 ± 23.37	0.4
	2nd	39.31 ± 21.82	
	3rd	34.13 ± 22.46	
Parameter	Abortion	Mean ± SD	P-value
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	No	31.99 ± 17.68	0.05

Parameter	Residency	Mean ± SD	P-value
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	1-3	38.54 ± 24.01	0.3
	Rural	35.00 ± 21.02	
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	Urban	38.56 ± 24.18	0.1
	Fair	37.58 ± 23.12	
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	Good	31.26 ± 17.69	0.05
	Housewife	37.21 ± 22.64	
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	Employed	28.65 ± 17.25	0.7
	<3	35.73 ± 22.72	
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	≥3	36.92 ± 21.97	0.02
	No	34.66 ± 20.78	
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	Yes	45.71 ± 27.86	0.6
	No	36.99 ± 23.20	
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	Yes	35.06 ± 20.35	0.7
	No	38.29 ± 24.22	
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	1-3	35.33 ± 21.88	0.7
	>3	36.58 ± 18.74	

Discussion

The present study examined the hematological profile of pregnant women, with a particular focus on hemoglobin (Hb), packed cell volume (PCV), and serum iron levels, in relation to demographic, socioeconomic, and reproductive factors. The findings demonstrated that gestational trimester was the strongest determinant of both Hb and PCV, while serum iron showed unique associations with abortion history and occupational status. These results shed light on both physiological and socio-behavioral influences on maternal hematological health. A key observation was the significant reduction in Hb and PCV during the third trimester compared to earlier stages of pregnancy. This aligns with the well-documented physiological hemodilution of pregnancy, where plasma volume expansion outpaces the rise in red cell mass, leading to a decline in measured indices of oxygen-carrying capacity [12]. Similar findings were reported by Young et al., who showed that the prevalence of anemia peaks in late gestation due to heightened iron requirements and dilutional changes [13]. A recent Iraqi study by Abdilahi et al. also confirmed that Hb values were lowest in the third trimester, emphasizing the need for trimester-specific reference ranges to avoid overdiagnosis of anemia in early pregnancy [14]. The clinical implication is that while mild anemia in the third trimester may be physiological, continued monitoring is essential to identify superimposed nutritional deficiencies. Interestingly, most demographic and socioeconomic variables, including age, BMI, education, residency, and

income, showed no significant association with Hb or PCV in this cohort. This is consistent with the findings of El-Kholy et al., who noted that when women receive basic antenatal supplementation, demographic differences exert only a minor effect on hemoglobin levels [15]. However, it should be noted that the majority of participants in the present study were housewives from rural areas with limited education, which may have reduced variability in socioeconomic characteristics. Other studies, particularly in multiethnic or more socioeconomically diverse populations, have highlighted stronger associations between maternal education, income, and hematologic status [16,17]. This suggests that the role of socioeconomic factors may be context-dependent and less evident in relatively homogeneous populations. Serum iron patterns in this study differed from those of Hb and PCV. Women with a history of abortion had significantly higher serum iron levels than those without such history. One possible explanation is that women who experienced abortions may have received iron supplementation post-abortion or may have altered iron metabolism related to repeated blood loss and recovery. Similar findings were reported in an Egyptian cohort by Malek-mellouli M et al., who noted elevated serum iron levels among women with prior pregnancy loss, likely due to clinical emphasis on supplementation during subsequent pregnancies [18]. In addition, housewives showed higher serum iron levels compared to employed women. This may reflect differences in diet, stress exposure, or compliance with

supplementation. Employed women, particularly in resource-limited settings, may face barriers to consistent nutritional intake or antenatal follow-up, as suggested by studies from South Asia and the Middle East [19]. It is also notable that BMI did not significantly influence hematological indices in this cohort. Some previous studies have demonstrated a link between obesity and altered iron metabolism, often mediated by chronic inflammation and hepcidin upregulation, leading to functional iron deficiency [20]. However, in the present study, overweight women actually had slightly higher Hb levels, though not statistically significant. This could be due to small sample size, or it may suggest that obesity-related inflammation is less pronounced in younger populations with shorter exposure to metabolic disorders. The limited impact of parity and gravidity on Hb, PCV, and iron status in this study is in line with the work of Uche-Nwachi EO et al., who observed that parity alone does not predict anemia when nutritional supplementation and antenatal care are available [21]. Nonetheless, the high proportion of multigravida women in this cohort raises concerns regarding cumulative nutritional depletion, especially in resource-constrained households. Routine iron supplementation throughout pregnancy remains essential to mitigate this risk.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated that gestational trimester was the main determinant of hemoglobin and PCV, with significant reductions observed in the third trimester due to physiological hemodilution. Serum iron showed unexpected associations, being higher among women with a history of abortion and lower among employed women. Socio-demographic factors such as age, education, and income had limited influence on hematological indices in this cohort. These findings highlight the importance of trimester-specific monitoring and targeted interventions for at-risk subgroups to optimize maternal hematologic health.

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